

BACTERICIDAL AND BACTERIOSTATIC ACTIVITIES OF AQUEOUS EXTRACTS OF *Citrus sinensis* PEELS IN SELECTED *IN VITRO* BACTERIAL STRAINS.

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Abstract

The antibacterial activity of aqueous extract of the peels of *Citrus sinensis* were assessed against bacterial isolates of *Escherichia coli* ATCC 29214, *Salmonella Enterica Typhimurium* ATCC 14028, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 14579, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 15315, *Shigella flexneri* ATCC 120233, *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A, *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 7644, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25823, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213 *in vitro* at concentration 1000mg/ml, 750mg/ml, 500mg/ml, 250mg/ml, 125mg/ml and 62.5mg/ml. Results showed that the aqueous extract had antibacterial activities against test bacteria but to varying degrees. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A and *Salmonella Enterica typhimurium* ATCC 14028 were found to be at 500mg/ml while *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 7644, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 29214, and *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 14579 had MIC at 750mg/ml and *Shigella flexneri* ATCC 120233 was found to be at 1000mg/ml. This shows that the aqueous peels extract of *Citrus sinensis* possess antibacterial compounds that act against groups of bacteria that are responsible for most bacterial diseases.

Introduction

Diarrhea is characterized by the alteration of the bowel movement and the increase in the water content, volume or frequency of stools, and abdominal pain [1]. Diarrheal diseases are a major problem in the developing countries and are responsible for million people death each year, with more than 600 000 deaths due to shigellosis [2]. The natural reservoir of this strain is the human gastrointestinal tract and especially the colon [3].

Shigella is one of the leading bacterial causes of diarrhea worldwide. In 2012, World Health Organization revealed insufficient data exist, but conservative estimates suggest *Shigella* causes about

90 million cases of severe dysentery, with at least 100,000 of these resulting in death each year, mostly among children in the developing world. Some *Shigella* has become resistant to antibiotics and inappropriate use of antibiotics to treat shigellosis can make the organisms more resistant in the future. Antibiotics commonly used are ampicillin, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, nalidixic acid, the fluoroquinolone, ciproflaxin. Resistance to quinolone antibiotics has been reported for this organism which rapidly develops resistance to the current therapy [4]. Studies have shown that multidrug resistant isolates are becoming

prevalent in sub-Saharan Africa owing to travel among individuals from various countries in the region [5]. This situation leads scientists to search for new sources of antimicrobial substances from various sources like medicinal plants [6].

In Africa, some medicinal plants are currently used against bacillary dysentery. The use of plants as remedies generally possesses advantages over many synthetic antimicrobial agents. They contain minerals, vitamins, anti-oxidants and other unique nutrients which possess biological activities; confers immunity and improves the general wellbeing of users [7].

Reports say that citrus fruits possess the highest antioxidant activity [8][9]. *Citrus sinensis* belongs to family *Rutaceae* and is cultivated throughout the world for its nutritional value. Flavonoids and vitamins in *C. sinensis* have been reported to exhibit strong anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties [10-12, 7]. Flavonoids have also been reported to decrease low-density lipoprotein, cholesterol, Apo lipoprotein B and triglycerides in rats [13], rabbits [14] and humans [15]. Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) production in Nigeria is significant. According to Food and Agriculture Organization [16], Nigeria produces 3 percent of world's fruits annually, contributing 3,240,000 tonnes to Africa's total amount of 3,741,000.

Suitable methods have to be adopted to utilize orange peel and pulp for the conversion into value-added products. The citrus peels are rich in nutrients and contain many phytochemicals, possess antimicrobial activity and can be efficiently used as drugs or as food supplements. There is an increase in the number of

antibiotic resistance pathogens, there is always a search of an alternative drug that is regarded as safe [17]. This work is aimed at assaying for the antibacterial activity of *Citrus sinensis* against selected bacterial strains.

Materials and Methods

Source of plant extracts

Citrus sinensis fruits were obtained from some vendors around Ugbowo. The fruits were identified by Dr. M. E. Osawaru at the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria.

Preparation of plant extracts

Fruits were washed and peeled with knife. Peels were dried in the laboratory at room temperature for 2 weeks. Peels were then grinded with a blender and weighed. Extract were prepared in order to study their antibacterial activity with slight modification of the method of [18]. A known quantity of peel powder (30g) was macerated in 200mls of distilled water and then left for 48 hours with occasional stirring with a sterile glass rod. The content of flask was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper and evaporated to dryness using a steam bath at 100°C. The filtrate had a dark green colour after the completion of the extraction. After evaporation, the extract was recovered and weighed (2.18g).

Bacterial isolates

Reference strains *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A, *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 7644, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 29214, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25823,

Salmonella Enterica typhimurium ATCC 14028, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 14579, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 15315, *Shigella flexneri* ATCC 120233, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213 used in this study were sub cultured onto solidified nutrient and *Salmonella-Shigella* agar plates and incubated at a temperature of 37°C for 24 hours [19].

Preparation of Inoculum

Broth cultures of the isolates were prepared by transferring two or three isolated colonies to Nutrients broth and incubated at 37°C for 4 to 6 hours. The cultures were checked for turbidity by comparing with McFarland Standard (0.5). This turbidity was equivalent to approximately 1×10^8 colony-forming units per milliliter (cfu/ml). The suspension was used for further testing [19].

Agar well diffusion method

Agar well diffusion method was employed. An overnight culture of test organisms was standardized to contain approximately 10^8 cfu/ml was inoculated into molten nutrient agar. The culture medium was allowed to set. Thereafter, a sterile cork borer was used to punch wells in the seeded nutrient agar. The agar plugs were removed with a flamed cooled the wire loop. Into the separate well was poured different concentrations of the plants extracts. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and zone of inhibition was measured [20].

Results and Discussion

The antibacterial activity of aqueous *Citrus sinensis* peels extract was assayed *in vitro* by agar well diffusion method. Table 1 summarizes the microbial growth inhibition of aqueous extracts of *C. sinensis* peels. The aqueous extract of *C. sinensis* peels had conspicuous zone of inhibition. The inhibition zones ranged between 11mm and 20mm at aqueous peels extract concentration of 1000mg/ml. Aqueous extract of *C. sinensis* peels at different concentrations (1000, 750, 500, 250, 125, 62.50 mg/ml) exhibited moderate antibacterial activity against *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A, *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 7644, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 29214, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25823, *Salmonella Enterica typhimurium* ATCC 14028, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 14579, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 15315, *Shigella flexneri* ATCC 120233, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213, in a dose-dependent manner.

The Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations (MBCs) of aqueous extract of *C. sinensis* peels on test bacterial isolates are represented on table 2. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25823, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 15315 and *Salmonella Enterica Typhimurium* ATCC 14028 were found to be at 500mg/ml while *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 7644, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 29214,

Table 1: Zones of inhibition (mm) exhibited by aqueous *C. sinensis* peels extract on test bacterial isolates.

Bacterial isolates	1000 mg/ml	750 mg/ml	500 mg/ml	250 mg/ml	125 mg/ml	62.50 mg/ml
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> Scott A	19	13	11	0	0	0
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ATCC 7644	14	10	0	0	0	0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 25823	17	12	10	0	0	0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 25923	18	13	10	0	0	0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 29213	13	9	0	0	0	0
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ATCC 14579	16	11	0	0	0	0
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i> ATCC 15315	19	13	11	0	0	0
<i>Shigella flexneri</i> ATCC 120233	11	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 29214	15	11	0	0	0	0
<i>Salmonella Enterica typhimurium</i> ATCC 14028	20	14	11	0	0	0

Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 29213 and *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 14579 had MIC at 750mg/ml and *Shigella flexneri* ATCC 120233 was found to be at 1000mg/ml. The MBCs remained constant at 1000mg/ml for all bacterial isolates except *L. monocytogenes* Scott A, *Salmonella Enterica Typhimurium* ATCC 14028 and *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 15315 which were 750mg/ml.

This study revealed moderate *in vitro* antibacterial activity against test bacterial isolates at higher concentrations varying from 500mg/ml to 1000mg/ml (Table 1) while at lower concentration ranging from 250mg/ml to 62.5mg/ml, no inhibition zone was observed suggesting that the antibacterial activity of aqueous *Citrus sinensis* peels extract is concentration dependent. There was variation in the sensitivities of the test isolates to *C. sinensis* peels extract. This could be due to the inability of the extract to permeate the cell of the organisms or possession of drug inactivating enzymes mediated by plasmid or chromosome of the bacterium. This study is in line with the work of Nannapaneni [21] which showed that *C. sinensis* peels had inhibitory effects on

Table 2: MICs and MBCs of aqueous *C. sinensis* peels extract on test bacterial isolates

Bacterial isolates	Minimum Inhibitory concentrations (MICs) (mg/ml)	Minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs) (mg/ml)
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> Scott A	500	750
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ATCC 7644	750	1000
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 25823	500	1000
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 25923	500	1000
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 29213	750	1000
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ATCC 14579	750	1000
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i> ATCC 15315	500	750
<i>Shigella flexneri</i> ATCC 120233	1000	1000
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 29214	750	1000
<i>Salmonella Enterica typhimurium</i> ATCC 14028	500	750

strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* and some pathogenic bacteria apparently due to the inherent phytochemicals in the peels.

This study revealed that *C. sinensis* peels extract had antimicrobial effects on a range of Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria [21]. Doughari and Manzara [22] suggested that it can be used in the development of safe antibiotics in the treatment of bacterial infections. Based on the results of Pourhossein [23], using dried *C. sinensis* peels reduced *Escherichia coli*. Gram negative bacteria have been reported as being more resistant to antimicrobial agents due to the presence of an outer-membrane permeability barrier, which limits access of the antimicrobial agents to their targets in the bacterial cell [24]. The antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* ATCC 29214, *Salmonella Enterica typhimurium* ATCC 14028, *Shigella flexneri* ATCC 120233 and *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 15315 (Gram negative) and *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A, *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 7644, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25823, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213 and *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 14579 (Gram positive) bacteria used in this study is an indication of its broad spectrum of activity at higher concentrations (Table 2). This observation is similar to earlier reports of Doughari and Manzara [22], [17], [24]. Lambert [25] showed that the differences in sensitivity between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria to the extract can probably be attributed to the structural and compositional differences in membranes between the two groups

which is line with our study. The low MICs is an indication of high efficacy of *C. sinensis* peels extract against bacterial isolates while high MIC may indicate minimal efficacy or possible development of resistance by the bacterial isolates to the peels extract [26].

The antimicrobial potency of plants is believed to be due to tannins, saponins, phenolic compounds, essential oils and flavonoids [27]. These compounds are known to be biologically active and therefore aid the antimicrobial activities of the plants. These secondary metabolites exert antimicrobial activity through different mechanisms [28]. Singh and Bhat [29] reported that flavonoids are responsible for the antibacterial activity associated with some medicinal plants. Tannin as observed in *C. sinensis* peels extract has been found to form irreversible complexes with proline rich protein resulting in the inhibition of cell protein synthesis [30].

Conclusion

Pathogenic bacteria are becoming resistant to available antibiotics. Possibilities for resistance spread are also on the increase. The peels of *citrus sinensis* fruits are considered to be waste product of citrus processing industries. In this study, the aqueous peels extract of *C. sinensis* exhibited inhibitory effect against selected bacterial isolates. The antibacterial efficacy of the peels extract can be ascribed to the presence of secondary metabolites. The peels can therefore be used in the treatment of some infections caused by these bacterial agents.

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